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WILD, DOMESTICATED, NATIVE: HUMANS-BEES
RELATIONSHIP IN CULTURAL ANTHROPOLOGY

Selvatiche, addomesticate, autoctone: le interazioni dell'uomo con le api

Human's relationship with animals is a classic topic of cultural anthropology inquiry and thus extensive literature focuses on the ways humans build their relationship with animals. Particularly, most classics work on human-animal relationships linger on the study of totemic power, hunters-gathers societies, husbandry, as well as ecological knowledge, and sexual innuendo. More recently, the study of how humans think, work, live, and consume animals develop in two pivotal fields of research, that is Human-Animal Studies (HAS) and Critical Human-Animal Studies (CAS) (DE MELLO, 2012; MARVIN & MCHUGH, 2014). Nevertheless, the majority of these contribution focuses on the study of humans in relation to a specific category of animals, mammals. In this regard, the emergence of multispecies theories seems to have offered the opportunity to critically reflect on the relationship between humans and other species and to reposition the 'human' in these relations (KIRKSEY & HELMREICH, 2010). Drawing from four years-ethnographic research, the paper aims to explore how the concepts of 'wild,' 'domesticated,' and 'native' are built in the field of beekeeping. Although these categories are often taken for granted, particularly from a scholarly ecological knowledge perspective, these notions are culturally constructed (ESCOBAR, 1998). That is, native species appear often to belong to the category of 'wild species,' while non-native species seem to be considered 'domesticated.' By taking on a multispecies approach, the contribution shows how the concepts are negotiated, constructed, and deconstructed in humans-pollinators relationships. Finally,

the paper shows how certain categories applied to specific species may mirror forms of racism in human societies (TSING, 1995; HARAWAY, 2008).

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